

Spectral and Conformational Analyses of Humosine A

LONG-ZE LIN^a, ROBERTO R. GIL^a, SHU-FANG HU^a, GEOFFREY A. CORDELL^{*a}, ANGELA Y LEE^b and JON CLARDY^b

^aProgram for Collaborative Research in the Pharmaceutical Sciences, Department of Medicinal Chemistry and Pharmacognosy, College of Pharmacy, University of Illinois at Chicago, Chicago, Illinois 60612, U.S.A.

^bDepartment of Chemistry, Baker Laboratory, Cornell University, Ithaca, NY 14853-1301, U.S.A.

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The spectral and conformational analyses of humosine A (corytensine), a phthalideisoquinoline hemiacetal alkaloid from *Corydalis humosa*, were obtained by a combination of 1D nmr techniques and computer modelling, and its X-ray structure confirmed.

Humosine A (**1**), a phthalideisoquinoline alkaloid, was first isolated from *Corydalis humosa* Miga by Chao *et al.* in 1966 and showed convulsive properties *in vivo*¹. In this publication, the authors only reported the ir spectrum of the compound, its HCl salt, and its m.p. and $[\alpha]_D$, and no nmr data or a detailed structure determination were reported. In 1986, several alkaloids were isolated from this plant by us. One of them was found to be humosine A on the basis of its identical ir spectrum to that reported previously, and its structure and conformation were elucidated by single crystal X-ray analysis in P. R. China². In 1988, Wu *et al.* reported the isolation and structure determination of an alkaloid from *C. ochotensis* Turcz. which was given the name corytensine³. Its structure was determined also by a single crystal X-ray analysis, but the stereochemistry of C-9 was incorrectly written in the reported formula. In 1990⁴, an erratum was reported correcting this error, but the authors ignored the fact that the corrected structure was identical to that determined previously for humosine A. Later it was recognised that corytensine and humosine A are the same compound⁵. In addition, in 1989 the synthetic alkaloids, (+)-*epi*- α -decumbensine and (-)-decumbensine⁶ were shown to be different from the natural isolate reported from *Corydalis decumbens*⁷, and subsequent synthetic work demonstrated that these

compounds are humosine A (corytensine) and its natural diastereomer egenine (**2**), respectively^{5,8-10}. Humosine A was also recently reported from two other *Corydalis* species^{11,12}. Although the ¹H and ¹³C nmr data of **1** were described previously, thus far, there is no complete ¹³C nmr assignment in the literature; only those carbons bearing hydrogen which could be assigned by the HETCOR technique¹⁰.

From the literature, there are only three natural phthalideisoquinoline hemiacetals reported, namely, (+)-humosine A (corytensine) (**1**), (+)-egenine (**2**)¹³ and (-)-narcotine hemiacetal (**3**)¹⁴. Using computer modelling, we could explain the unusual chemical shift of the NMe (δ 1.96) in the ¹H nmr spectrum of **1**, as well as the significant difference in the chemical shift of H-2' observed between **1** and **2**. In this report, the complete ¹³C nmr assignments, and the use of computer-assisted conformational analysis to explain the ¹H nmr data of **1** are presented, and the X-ray crystal structure confirmed.

Results and Discussion

Humosine A (corytensine), a phthalideisoquinoline alkaloid from several *Corydalis* species (Papaveraceae), has been established to have the structure **1** with three asymmetric carbons :

1*R*, 9*S* and 7'*R*^{2,4}. The ¹H nmr spectrum (500 MHz; CDCl₃) showed a singlet at δ 1.96 for

1. (+)-Humosine A

2. (+)-Egenine

3. (-)-Narcotine hemiacetal

the NMe group, five one-proton singlets at δ 3.68, 5.28, 6.25, 6.61 and 6.72, one two-proton AB system signal at δ 6.84 (2H, H-2' and H-3'), two methylenedioxy groups at δ 5.90 (1H, d, *J* 1.5 Hz), 5.95 (1H, d, *J* 1.5 Hz), 6.03 (1H, d, *J* 1.5 Hz) and 6.08 (1H, d, *J* 1.5 Hz), and two vicinal methylene groups at δ 3.20 (1H, ddd, *J* 15.5, 12.5, 3 Hz), 2.47 (1H, dt, *J* 15.5, ~3 Hz), 2.54 (1H, ddd, *J* 12.5, 10.5, 2.5 Hz) and 3.00 (1H, dt, *J* 10.5, ~3 Hz). The assignments of these signals were performed by nOe difference experiment. The nOe difference irradiation of the NMe signal enhanced the two-proton AB signal at δ 6.85 (H-2' and H-3'), and the one-proton signal at δ 3.68, consequently, the latter should be assigned to H-1. Irradiation of the H-1 signal enhanced the signals at δ 1.96, 6.85, 6.72 and 5.28, which led to the assignment of the last two signals as H-8 and H-9, respectively. Similarly, irradiation of the H-9 signal enhanced the signals of H-1, H-8 and H-2', and irradiation of the H-8 signal enhanced the H-1 and H-9 signals. Irradiation of one of the methylene signals at δ 2.47 enhanced an aromatic proton signal at δ 6.61, the signal of the remaining aromatic proton H-5, and its geminal partner proton signal at δ 3.20. Thus, these two protons should be the H-4 methylene protons, and their two vicinal proton signals at δ 2.54 and 3.00 must be the signals of the H-3 protons, as confirmed by the CSCM 1D nmr technique¹⁵. The remaining singlet at δ 6.25 should be the signal for the H-7' proton. There is no nOe correlation between the methylenedioxy and any other groups, thus, the two sets of signals of the two methylenedioxy groups were assigned by the selective INEPT technique^{16,17}

All of the protons attached to carbon were assigned by the CSCM 1D nmr technique, and the selective INEPT technique was used to assign the carbons two or three bonds away from a proton. The aromatic protons were irradiated with *J* 8–10 Hz to enhance the carbons three bonds away, aliphatic methylene and methine

TABLE 1—¹H AND ¹³C NMR DATA AND RESULTS OF SELECTIVE INEPT EXPERIMENTS*

Position	¹ H	¹³ C	Selective INEPT (carbon)**
1	3.68 (s)	68.45	(NCH ₃), (9), 1'
2	—	—	—
3α	3.00 (dt, 10.5, 3)	53.74	1, 4a
3β	2.54 (ddd, 12.5, 10.5, 2.5)	—	1, 4a
4α	3.20 (ddd, 15.5, 12.5, 3)	29.16	(3), (4a), 5, 8a
4β	2.47 (dt, 15.5, 3)	—	(3), (4a), 5, 8a
4a	—	128.49	—
5	6.61 (s)	108.12	(4a), (6), 7, 8a
6	—	146.05	—
7	—	146.30	—
8	6.72 (s)	106.76	1, 4a, 6
8a	—	130.40	—
9	5.28 (s)	89.71	11, (1'), 2', 6', 7'
1'	—	135.09	—
2'	6.85 (AB)	114.35	9, 4', 6'
3'	6.85 (AB)	109.43	1', 5'
4'	—	148.12	—
5'	—	142.21	—
6'	—	124.45	—
7'	6.25 (s)	97.65	1', 5' (6')
NMe	1.96 (s)	47.25	1, 3
6,7-OCH ₂ O	5.90 (d, 1.5)	101.45	6, 7
6,7'-OCH ₂ O	5.95 (d, 1.5)	—	6, 7
4',5'-OCH ₂ O	6.03 (d, 1.5)	102.41	4', 5'
4',5'-OCH ₂ O	6.08 (d, 1.5)	—	4', 5'

* Recorded in CDCl₃, chemical shift values are reported as δ values (ppm) from TMS at 500.12 MHz for ¹H and 90.8 MHz for ¹³C, signal multiplicity and coupling constants (Hz) are shown in parentheses

** Selective INEPT experiments were performed at 90.8 MHz with *J* 8 Hz for aromatic protons, *J* 6 Hz for aliphatic protons and *J* 4 Hz for the dioxymethylene protons, two bond correlations are shown in parentheses

protons were irradiated with *J* 6 Hz, except for methylenedioxy protons, for which a *J* value of 4 Hz was used¹⁷. Carbons-2' and -3' were distinguished by the selective INEPT irradiation of H-9, which is three bonds away from C-2'. Similarly, C-1' and C-6' were distinguished by the irradiation of H-1, and C-5', and C-4' by the irradiation of H-7'. Irradiation of the methylenedioxy proton signal at δ 6.03 and 6.08 enhanced C-4' and C-5', and the irradiation of the other OCH₂O signals at δ 5.90 and 5.95 enhanced C-6 and C-7; thus, they were assigned unambiguously. All of the ¹H and ¹³C nmr data, as well as the principal results of

the selective INEPT experiments, are presented in Table 1. The ¹H nmr assignments are similar to those of corytensine deduced from the results of nOe experiments, except that the two methylenedioxy groups were not assigned by Wu *et al.*³.

The X-ray crystallographic analysis of humosine A has also been performed and results similar to those reported previously^{2,3} have been obtained.

The structure of humosine A (1) was generated by the molecular modeling program PCMODEL 386 V 4.0 using the MMX force field. Humosine A was built and minimised with the same stereochemistry and conformation obtained from the X-ray analysis. The six-membered nitrogen containing ring is in the half-chair conformation with N-2 and C-3' on opposite sides of the plane defined by C-1, C-8a, C-4a, C-4. The orientation (axial or equatorial) for H-3, H-4 and the NMe group in this conformer is given in Table 2 and shown in Fig. 1—structure 1a. The other conformer 1b and the conformers

TABLE 2—ORIENTATION (AXIAL (AX) OR EQUATORIAL (EQ)) OF H-3, H-4 AND THE NMe GROUP IN THE CONFORMERS 1a, 1b, 2a AND 2b

	1a	1b	2a	2b
H-3α	eq	ax	eq	ax
H-3β	ax	eq	ax	eq
H-4α	ax	eq	ax	eq
H-4β	eq	ax	eq	ax
NMe	eq	ax	eq	ax

2a and 2b for egenine were also generated and are listed in Table 2, with the structures given in Fig. 2. For all of the minimisations, the hydrogen bond between the hemiacetal OH and the nitrogen atom were considered. The relative potential energies of each conformer are listed in Table 3. As can be seen from this table, in the case of humosine A, the lowest energy conformation is the one in which the NMe group occupies an equatorial orientation, but in the case of egenine this conformation is one in which the NMe group occupies an axial orientation. In the case of (+)-humosine

TABLE 3—RELATIVE ENERGY (E), CALCULATED HYDROGEN BOND N(2)...HO(7') DISTANCE, AND CALCULATED VS EXPERIMENTAL VICINAL J VALUES^a

	1	1a	1b	2	2a	2b
E (kcal mol ⁻¹)	—	0.00	5.97	—	6.88	3.51
H bond (Å)	—	1.795	1.790	—	1.872	1.793
$J_{3\alpha-4\alpha}$	~3	2.6 (63) ^b	4.8 (47)	**	2.4 (65)	4.9 (47)
$J_{3\alpha-4\beta}$	~3	3.3 (55)	12.0 (165)	**	3.5 (54)	11.9 (164)
$J_{3\beta-4\alpha}$	12.5	12.5 (178)	1.7 (66)	**	12.5 (177)	1.7 (66)
$J_{3\beta-4\beta}$	2.5	2.4 (61)	4.8 (51)	**	2.3 (62)	4.9 (50)
J_{1-9}	*	1.1 (64)	1.9 (102)	3.9	5.1 (43)	3.2 (58)

^aValues given for **1a**, **1b**, **2a** and **2b** are the calculated ones. ^bValues given in parentheses are the calculated dihedral angles between the vicinal protons, which were used to estimate the J values. *Not observed because signal is a broad singlet. **Not reported in the literature.

Fig. 1. Three-dimensional views of **1a**, **1b**, **2a** and **2b**.

A, this is the same conformation that the molecule adopts in the solid state as shown by the X-ray analysis. Although there is no X-ray analysis reported for (+)-egenine (**2**), (–)-narcotine hemiacetal (**3**) (an alkaloid with the same relative,

but opposite absolute stereochemistry as egenine) shows a conformation in the solid state in which the NMe group is in an axial orientation¹⁸. It is interesting to note that when the conformers were minimised without considering the formation

of the hydrogen bond, not only were the energies higher, but also the difference of energy between them in both compounds was close to zero. This explains why in all of the alkaloids the NMe group and the hemiacetal OH adopt a configuration in which it is possible to form the hydrogen bond stabilising the molecule, as observed in the calculations. To be more specific, when the hydrogen bond is present, the NMe group is in a *cis* relationship with H-1, as well as H-9 with H-7'. For humosine A, as discussed above, nOe enhancements were observed between H-1 and the NMe, but not between H-9 and H-7'. This is because the 5-membered ring adopts an envelope conformation with H-9 and H-7' in a pseudoequatorial orientation and the distances observed in the model for these two protons is 3.839 Å, while the distance between H-1 and the NMe protons is 2.388 Å. In the future isolation or synthesis of this alkaloid type, this observation should be considered in order to assign the relative stereochemistries of C-1, C-9 and C-7'.

The vicinal coupling constants involving protons H-3 and H-4, and H-1 and H-9 were estimated from the calculated dihedral angles. PCMODEL calculates the *J* values using the Karplus generalised equation developed by Haasnoot *et al.*¹⁹. Calculated *J* values vs experimental values are given in Table 3. The experimental values for humosine A are in good agreement with those calculated for the lower energy conformer **1a**. The calculated value of J_{1-9} 1.11 Hz explains the multiplicity observed for this pair of protons which appear as broad singlets. Unfortunately, there are no coupling constant values involving H-3 and H-4 reported for egenine. Only J_{1-9} 3.9 Hz is available for this compound, which is quite close to the calculated value. In the case of narcotine hemiacetal (**3**) this coupling constant is 4.22 Hz. Another opportunity that we had with the modelling program was to determine the origin of the unusual chemical shift observed for the N-methyl group protons. This NCH₃ group normally falls in the range

of 2.4–2.6 ppm. In the case of humosine A, the observed chemical shift was 1.96 ppm. It is possible to see in the model of the preferred conformation **1a** that the NCH₃ group is under the influence of the shielding magnetic field produced by the ring current of the aromatic ring of the phthalide moiety. On the other hand, the chemical shifts of the protons of H-2' and H-3' in humosine A are almost the same, both protons appearing as an AB system centered at δ 6.85 in ¹H nmr. However, in egenine (**2**) and narcotine hemiacetal (**3**) these two protons show very different chemical shifts. In **2**, H-2' and H-3' appear at δ 5.64, and 6.53, and in **3** at δ 5.79 and 6.64 respectively. As can be observed, there is a strong influence of H-2' in both cases. Looking at the model, we found that H-2', in both conformers of egenine (**2a** and **2b**), is almost in the center of the cone of influence of the aromatic ring of the isoquinoline group.

Experimental

The ¹H nmr spectrum of **1** was obtained on a GE OMEGA 500 spectrometer operating at 500.1 MHz using a solution of **1** (10 mg) in CDCl₃ (0.5 ml). The nOe difference spectra were run on a Varian XL-300 instrument. CSCM 1D, selective INEPT spectra of **1** were taken in a Nicolet NT-360 spectrometer operating at 90.8 MHz, with *J* 8 Hz for aromatic protons, 6 Hz for aliphatic protons, and 4 Hz for the protons of the OCH₂O groups.

The tubers of *C. humosa* were collected in 1984, in Jiansu Province, P. R. China, and identified by Dr. X.-L. Huang. Voucher samples are deposited in the herbarium of Shanghai Institute of Materia Medica, Chinese Academy of Sciences, Shanghai, P. R. China.

Isolation of humosine A (1) : The powdered dry tubers (2 kg) of *C. humosa* were extracted with EtOH at room temperature, the residue was extracted with 1% HCl, and the acidic solution was basified to pH 9 with concentrated

NH₃ solution and extracted with CHCl₃. The CHCl₃ solution was concentrated to obtain an alkaloid extract (8 g), which was subjected to repeated cc, eluted with CHCl₃, CHCl₃-MeOH mixtures and finally MeOH to obtain humosine A (**1**; 20 mg, 0.001%), protopine (2.5 g, 0.125%), tetrahydrocoptisine (1 g, 0.05%) and bicucculine (200 mg, 0.01%). The known alkaloids were identified through comparison with the m.p., [α]_D, ir, and other physical data of the standard samples of protopine, tetrahydrocoptisine and bicucculine. Humosine A was identified by the reported m.p., [α]_D and ir spectrum¹. Humosine A also has an identical m.p., [α]_D, cd, uv, ir, ms, ¹H and ¹³C nmr data to those of corytensine³. The assignment of the ¹H and ¹³C nmr spectra are shown in Table 1.

Single crystal X-ray diffraction analysis of 1: A colourless block (0.16 × 0.28 × 0.6 mm) was chosen for analysis and used in all subsequent experiments. The analysis was carried out on a Siemens R3m diffractometer using graphite monochromated CuKα radiation (1.5418 Å) at room temperature. Preliminary diffraction photographs showed orthorhombic symmetry, and accurate cell constants of $a = 7.646(3)$, $b = 12.953(5)$, $c = 17.001(7)$ Å were obtained from a least-squares fit of 25 diffractometer measured 2θ-values in the range $30^\circ \leq 2\theta \leq 45^\circ$. Systematic absences and density considerations uniquely fit space group P2₁2₁2₁ with one molecule of C₂₀H₁₉NO₆ in the asymmetric unit. A total of 2748 Friedel-redundant (two octants) reflections with $2\theta \leq 116^\circ$ were collected. After correction for Lorentz, polarisation and background effects, 2708 (99%), were judged observed ($|F_o| \geq 4\sigma(F_o)$) and used in subsequent refinement. The structure was solved uneventfully using the SHELXS system of programs. Anisotropic thermal parameters were employed for non-hydrogen atoms and hydrogen atoms were fixed geometrically with riding constraints. The final agreement factor was $R = 0.055$ with a goodness of fit of 1.74 for all the data. An attempt to establish the absolute configuration using both Hamilton's

test and the absolute structure method was inconclusive. Further details are available from the authors.

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